

CUSTOMER SATISFACTION TOWARDS BANKING SERVICES – A STUDY OF REWARI DISTRICT

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Abstract:

Business organizations are facing tough competition here no exemption for financial services or Banking industries. Customer service is an integral part of any organization it is necessary to identify the key success factors in terms of customer satisfaction. To develop and to sustain business any of the banks must have quality of customer service that can link up cordial relation with the customer and result in to the satisfaction level of the customer. In the present research an effort has done to measure satisfaction level of customer to bank located in Rewari District. For this purpose a questionnaire was designed and distributed among 130 account holders in different bank and 110 filled in questionnaire were received, out of these 100 valid questionnaires were found. To analyse the satisfaction of customer’s chi- square test were used and it is found that almost all the respondents are satisfied with the services provided by the bank irrespective of gender, age and occupation.

Key Words: Customer Satisfaction, ECS, Online Banking & Credit Card Service

Introduction:

In today’s competitive environment relationship marketing is critical to banking corporate success. Banking is a customer oriented services industry and Indian banks have started realising that business depends on client service and the satisfaction of the customer. This is compelling them to improve customer service and build relationships with customers.

There is little doubt that the proliferation of, and advancements in, Internet-based technologies have resulted in fundamental changes in how companies interact with their customers (Ibrahim et al, 2006; Bauer et al., 2005; Parasuraman and Zinkhan 2002). Banks and financial corporations have been at the forefront of this Internet and technology adoption process. Online banking refers to the automated delivery of banking products and services directly to customers through electronic communication channels, most notably the Internet. Online banking is also called E-banking or PC banking. (Pikkarainen, Karjaluoto, and Pahlila 2004) define Internet banking as an ‘Internet portal, through which customers can use different kinds of banking services ranging from bill payment to making investments’.

The Indian banking and financial sector has also welcomed this change. Today, more and more Indian banks are trying to differentiate themselves in a fiercely competitive industry. Not only this helps them align their offerings to the constantly evolving customer needs and developments in technology, it also serves to replace some of traditional bank functions, thereby reducing significant overheads associated with bank branches.

Review of Literature:

M. E. Dodderaju (2013) in his study” A Study on customer satisfaction towards public and private sector banking services with special reference to anantapur district of Andra Pradesh “observed that there is significance difference among the respondents according to their income leve and level of satisfaction. Whereas, there is no significance difference between occupation and satisfaction. Further he observed that there is a lack of customer relationship and aggressive marketing in public sector bank as compared to private sector bank.

Ravi. C. S & Kundan Basavaraj (2013) in his study “Customer Preference and satisfaction towards banking services with special reference to SHIVAMOGGA District in Karnataka “found that business and vehicles loan are fast moving than other services and overall satisfaction leve is 50% further, overall satisfaction on bank deposit schemes resulted positively while other service of baking still need to be given attention by focusing on customer issues.

Tavishi and Santosh Kumar (2013) in his study “An Empirical Study on Technology Adoption by Indian Banks” observed that the factors influencing the customers for the adoption of internet banking and mobile banking in India and hence investigate the influence of perceived usefulness, perceived eases of use and perceived risk on use of internet banking and mobile banking.

Dr. Nirmala Mohan & Dr. Florence John (2014) in his study “Customers Awareness and Satisfaction of Online Banking Services: An Analytical Study of Nationalized banks in India” found that most of the respondents are aware and satisfied with E-Banking activities of the bank, Further the researchers observed that

there is no significance difference among the respondents according to different age group and education qualification regarding the use of internet bank.

Objectives:

- ✓ To and banking environment prevailing in the Rewari district.
- ✓ To study the customer satisfaction towards banking services among the respondents of selected area.

Hypothesis:

H01 Customer satisfaction is same among the respondents towards the banking services with reference to their demographic characteristic

Research Methodology

The present study used Exploratory cum Descriptive research design. It is exploratory because, research wish to know the prevailing banking environment in the District Rewari. It is descriptive because, it analyze the level of satisfaction among the respondent according to age, gender and Occupation. Population of Rewari district constitute the universe of the study, Account holder in any bank constitute survey population for the study and individual were use as sample unit for the study. 100 respondents were selected through purposive sampling method according to age, gender and occupation. The structure questionnaire which was frame specifically for the purpose used to collect the primary data. The questionnaire divided in two parts. Viz. Part A belongs to demographic information, Part B belong to customer's satisfaction towards banking services. The statement are given below

Particulars	SS	S	N	DS	SDS
1. Deposit					
2. ATM					
3. ECS (Electronic Clearing Services)					
4. Fund Transfer					
5. Online banking					
6. Card					
7. Loan Services					

Further data were analysis with the help of frequency and chi –square test.

Results:

Table 1: Number of Bank Branches in Rewari District

Name of Bank	No. of Branches		Total	Name of Bank	No. of Branches		Total
	Rural	Urban			Rural	Urban	
Axis Bank	00	03	03	Indian Bank	00	01	01
ICICI Bank	00	04	04	HDFC	02	02	04
Equitas Small Finance Bank Ltd	00	01	01	Dena Bank	00	01	01
Corporation Bank	00	01	01	Gurgaon Gramin Bank	03	06	09
AU Small Finance Bank Ltd	00	01	01	Syndicate Bank	00	02	02
Vijaya Bank	01	01	02	Union Bank of India	00	03	03
SBI	02	11	13	Allahabad Bank	00	01	01
Indusind Bank Ltd.	01	01	02	IDBI	01	01	02
PNB	04	05	09	Bank of Baroda	00	02	02
OBC	01	04	05	Central Bank of India	00	01	01
Bank of India	00	01	01	Andhra Bank	00	01	01
Indian Overseas Bank	00	01	01	Bank Of Maharashtra	00	01	01
Canara Bank	00	02	02				
Total			45	Total			28

(Source: Compiled from website <http://ifscfinder.com/city/rewari/>)

Table 2: Customer Satisfaction towards Banking Services According to Gender

Services	Gender	SS	S	N	D	SD	Total	Chi Square Value	Result
Deposit	Male	30	17	03	00	00	50	.106>0.05	Not Sig.
	Female	26	24	00	00	00	50		
	Total	56	41	03	00	00	100		
ATM	Male	35	13	00	02	00	50	.399>0.05	Not Sig.
	Female	36	12	01	00	01	50		
	Total	71	23	01	02	01	100		
Fund transfer	Male	19	25	06	00	00	50	.701>0.05	Not Sig.
	Female	19	26	04	01	00	50		
	Total	38	51	10	01	00	100		

ECS	Male	02	10	37	01	00	50	.996>0.05	Not Sig.
	Female	02	09	38	01	00	50		
	Total	04	19	75	02	00	100		
Online Banking	Male	25	21	04	00	00	50	.711>0.05	Not Sig.
	Female	22	25	03	00	00	50		
	Total	47	46	07	00	00	100		
Card Services	Male	14	25	09	02	00	50	.043<0.05	Sig.
	Female	13	35	02	00	00	50		
	Total	27	60	11	02	00	100		
Loan	Male	10	18	17	05	00	50	.014<0.05	Sig.
	Female	08	33	08	01	00	50		
	Total	18	51	25	06	00	100		

(Source: Primary data collected through questionnaire in September 2017)

Table 2 revealed that there is no significance difference between male and female respondents regarding deposit, ATM, Electronic clearing services, fund transfer and online banking services, it means both groups i.e are equally satisfied with banking services. Whereas, there is a significance difference between male and female respondents in regards card services (Debit card, credit card etc.) and loan services provided by the bank at 95% level of significance. As far as card services and loan facilities are concerned female respondents are more satisfied than the male respondents.

Table 3: Customer Satisfaction towards Banking Services According to Age

Services	Gender	SS	S	N	D	SD	Total	Chi Square value	Result
Deposit	Below 30	36	18	01	00	00	55	.300>0.05	Not Sig.
	31-50	18	21	02	00	00	46		
	Above 50	02	02	00	00	00	04		
	Total	56	41	03	00	00	100		
ATM	Below 30	40	14	01	00	00	55	.584>0.05	Not Sig.
	31-50	29	09	00	02	01	46		
	Above 50	02	02	00	00	00	04		
	Total	71	25	01	02	01	100		
Fund Transfer	Below 30	23	26	06	00	00	55	.804>0.05	Not Sig.
	31-50	13	23	04	01	00	46		
	Above 50	02	02	00	00	00	04		
	Total	38	51	10	01	00	100		
ECS	Below 30	04	10	40	01	00	55	.417>0.05	Not Sig.
	31-50	00	07	33	01	00	46		
	Above 50	00	02	02	00	00	04		
	Total	04	19	75	02	00	100		
Online Banking	Below 30	29	23	03	00	00	55	.676>0.05	Not Sig.
	31-50	10	21	04	00	00	46		
	Above 50	02	02	00	00	00	04		
	Total	47	46	07	00	00	100		
Card Service	Below 30	24	26	04	01	00	55	.004<0.05	Sig.
	31-50	03	30	07	01	00	46		
	Above 50	00	04	00	00	00	04		
	Total	27	60	11	02	00	100		
Loan	Below 30	11	27	12	05	00	55	.375>0.05	Not Sig.
	31-50	05	23	12	01	00	46		
	Above 50	05	01	01	00	00	4		
	Total	18	51	25	06	00	100		

(Source: Primary data collected through questionnaire in September 2017)

Table 3 revealed that there is no significance difference among the respondent according to different age group in regards deposit, ATM service, ECS (Electronic clearing services), fund transfer, online banking and loan facilities is concerned. But there is significance difference in opinion among the respondents according to different age group in respect of card services provided by the bank, below 30 age group are more satisfied with this service at 95% level of significance.

Table 4: Customer Satisfaction towards Banking Services According to Occupation

Services	Occupation	SS	S	N	D	SD	Total	Chi Square Value	Result
Deposit	Business	09	03	00	00	00	12	.348>0.05	Not Sig.

	Services	27	28	03	00	00	58		
	Student	16	07	00	00	00	23		
	Housewife	02	00	00	00	00	02		
	Other	02	03	00	00	00	05		
	Total	56	41	03	00	00	100		
ATM	Business	10	02	00	00	00	12	.041<0.05	Sig.
	Services	40	16	00	02	00	58		
	Student	18	04	01	00	00	23		
	Housewife	01	01	00	00	00	02		
	Other	02	02	00	00	01	05		
	Total	71	25	01	02	01	100		
ECS	Business	00	04	08	00	00	12	.734>0.05	Not Sig.
	Services	03	11	43	01	00	58		
	Student	00	03	19	01	00	23		
	Housewife	00	00	02	00	00	02		
	Other	01	01	03	00	00	05		
	Total	04	19	75	02	00	100		
Fund transfer	Business	06	04	02	00	00	12	.358>0.05	Not Sig.
	Services	23	32	02	01	00	58		
	Student	06	13	04	00	00	23		
	Housewife	01	01	00	00	00	02		
	Other	02	01	02	00	00	05		
	Total	38	51	10	01	00	100		
Online banking services	Business	06	05	01	00	00	12	.137>0.05	Not Sig.
	Services	29	27	02	00	00	58		
	Student	11	10	02	00	00	23		
	Housewife	00	02	00	00	00	02		
	Other	01	02	02	00	00	05		
	Total	47	46	07	00	00	100		
Card services	Business	03	07	02	00	00	12	.781>0.05	Not Sig.
	Services	13	38	06	01	00	58		
	Student	08	12	02	01	00	23		
	Housewife	00	02	00	00	00	02		
	Other	03	01	01	00	00	05		
	Total	27	60	11	02	00	100		
Loan	Business	04	04	04	00	00	12	.696>0.05	Not Sig.
	Services	09	33	13	03	00	58		
	Student	03	11	06	03	00	23		
	Housewife	01	01	00	00	00	02		
	Other	01	02	02	00	00	05		
	Total	18	51	25	06	00	100		

(Source: Primary data collected through questionnaire in September 2017)

Table 4 revealed that there is no significance difference among the respondent according to different occupation in respect of deposit, ATM services, fund transfer, online banking, card services and loan services provided by the bank. Whereas, there is a significance difference among the respondent according to different occupation as far as ECS is concerned at 95% level of significance. Servicemen are more satisfied than the other occupation's respondents as far as ECS is concerned.

Conclusions:

Most of the respondents satisfied with the services provided by the bank like deposit services , ATM services, ECS, Fund transfer, online banking , card services and loan. According to gender female respondents are more satisfied with card services and loan than the male respondents, most of the respondents not aware about electronic clearing services. According to different age group below 30 year age group respondents are more satisfied about the services provided by the bank, In case of different occupation all category of respondents are satisfied with the services provided by the bank. Keeping in view of above it is suggested that bank should specifically public sector bank increase ATM service in small town and villages which helpful in financial inclusion of the rural India and cashless transaction. Further, there is also need to educate the people about the use of online banking, card services, use of ECS etc.

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